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Abstract. Ethics in scientific research is essential for institutional and social progress, and its proper management represents a pillar of academic integrity. **Objective:** To evaluate the influence of a proposed ethical model for managing scientific integrity on academic conduct and performance in Peruvian institutions. **Methodology:** Quantitative, with a non-experimental, cross-sectional design. Cases documented in Peruvian publications from 2010 to 2024 were analyzed. **Results:** These demonstrate a theoretically favorable institutional environment, with a high appreciation of transparency, ethical development, and flexibility, suggesting that the model enhances integrity and research quality. **Conclusion:** The implemented ethical model significantly impacts institutional academic integrity in Peru. **Keywords:** Management, ethical model, academic integrity, scientific research.

Gestión de la ética en la investigación científica, influencia en la integridad académica institucional.

Resumen. La ética en la investigación científica es esencial para el progreso institucional y social, y su gestión adecuada representa un pilar para la integridad académica. **Objetivo:** Evaluar la influencia de un modelo ético propuesto en la gestión de la integridad científica sobre la conducta y el desempeño académico en instituciones peruanas. **Metodología:** cuantitativa, con diseño no experimental y corte transversal. Se analizaron casos documentados en publicaciones peruanas de 2010 a 2024. **Resultados:** evidencian un entorno institucional teóricamente favorable, con alta apreciación de la transparencia, el desarrollo ético y la flexibilidad, sugiriendo que el modelo eleva la integridad y la calidad investigativa. **Conclusión:** el modelo ético gestionado impacta significativamente en la integridad académica institucional **Palabras clave:** Gestión, modelo ético, integridad académica, investigación científica.

Gestão ética na pesquisa científica: influência na integridade acadêmica institucional

Resumo. A ética na pesquisa científica é essencial para o progresso institucional e social, e sua gestão adequada representa um pilar para a integridade acadêmica. **Objetivo:** Avaliar a influência de um modelo ético proposto na gestão da integridade científica sobre o comportamento e o desempenho acadêmico em instituições peruanas. **Metodologia:** quantitativa, com desenho não experimental e corte transversal. Foram analisados casos documentados em publicações peruanas de 2010 a 2024. **Resultados:** evidenciam um ambiente institucional teoricamente favorável, com alta apreciação da transparência, do desenvolvimento ético e da flexibilidade, sugerindo que o modelo eleva a integridade e a qualidade investigativa. **Conclusão:** o modelo ético gerenciado impacta significativamente na integridade acadêmica institucional no Peru. **Palavras-chave:** Gestão, modelo ético, integridade acadêmica, pesquisa científica.

Gestion de l'éthique dans la recherche scientifique, influence sur l'intégrité académique institutionnelle

Résumé. L'éthique dans la recherche scientifique est essentielle pour le progrès institutionnel et social, et sa gestion adéquate représente un pilier pour l'intégrité académique. **Objectif :** Évaluer l'influence d'un modèle éthique proposé dans la gestion de l'intégrité scientifique sur le comportement et la performance académique dans les institutions péruviennes. **Méthodologie :** quantitative, avec un design non expérimental et une coupe transversale. Des cas documentés dans des publications péruviennes de 2010 à 2024 ont été analysés. **Résultats :** mettent en évidence un environnement institutionnel théoriquement favorable, avec une haute appréciation de la transparence, du développement éthique et de la flexibilité, suggérant que le modèle élève l'intégrité et la qualité investigativa. **Conclusion :** le modèle éthique géré impacte significativement l'intégrité académique institutionnelle au Pérou. **Mots clés:** Management, modèle éthique, intégrité académique, recherche scientifique.

1. Introduction

Academic integrity in scientific research is central to the stability and efficiency of Peruvian institutions. Work dynamics in this sector are influenced not only by academic factors but also by ethical strategies that strengthen researchers' sense of responsibility and motivation. In this context, the development of ethical models must consider a comprehensive approach that combines emotional, organizational, and structural factors. Blanch (2011) warns that changes in academic management can generate ethical risks when they are not accompanied by strategies that promote researchers' well-being. The increasing pressure to publish, coupled with demanding requirements, can lead to high levels of fraud, affecting the quality of science and the retention of talent within institutions. Therefore, it is essential to implement ethical models that mitigate these risks and reinforce researchers' academic integrity. On the other hand, Quintana (2000) analyzes the impact of reforms in the academic sector on human resource management, demonstrating how the lack of adequate ethical incentives can lead to decreased trust and increased staff turnover. His study highlights the need to establish mechanisms for recognizing and improving ethical conditions, key aspects within a model that seeks to strengthen integrity in the scientific sector. From a more recent perspective, Ruiz and Villavicencio (2020) emphasize the role of ethical resilience in academia, especially in crisis situations such as those revealed in Peru. The authors stress that institutional policies should prioritize integrity and support strategies for researchers, facilitating an environment that promotes their ethical and professional well-being. In this sense, an ethical model should not only focus on sanctions but also on recognizing honest effort, academic stability, and ethical growth.

Similarly, Linares and Meza (2021) address organizational integrity from an internal marketing perspective, emphasizing the importance of ethical communication, leadership, and transparent reward systems. Their analysis demonstrates that ethical strategies must be aligned with the institution's identity and culture, fostering an environment that strengthens employee loyalty and a sense of belonging.

Finally, Cherchiglia (2004) explores the evolution of ethical management in Latin America, highlighting the tensions between traditional models and new, flexible approaches. His study suggests that the implementation of ethical models must balance the needs of academic staff with the demands of the scientific system, ensuring that reforms do not violate ethical rights or compromise the well-being of researchers.

Within this framework, the proposed ethical model for Peruvian institutions is based on the need to improve trust and academic integrity by implementing strategies such as recognizing ethical practices, promoting institutional flexibility, and fostering ethical development. These actions will not only contribute to talent retention but will also impact the quality of science provided to society, thus reinforcing the fundamental purpose of research.

Scientific integrity is a fundamental pillar for the social and academic development of countries. In the Peruvian context, the right to ethical science is a key principle within national policies, guaranteeing universal access to truthful and reliable knowledge, as established by the National Code of Scientific Integrity (CONCYTEC, 2025). However, the continuous improvement of the academic system faces significant challenges, especially regarding human resource management in scientific institutions. These institutions play an essential role in generating knowledge for the population, particularly in vulnerable areas. Despite the importance of this aspect, the effective management of academic personnel has not yet reached its full potential, mainly due to a lack of innovative proposals that promote ethics and integrity in scientific organizations.

Since the first studies in the 2010s, such as those conducted by Saldaña- Gastulo et al. (2010), the importance of ethical and emotional factors in the academic environment has been widely recognized. The integrity of researchers, particularly in institutions that provide essential services such as science, is a determining factor for organizational success (Erazo & Riaño,

2021). In the academic sector, the concept of comprehensive ethics, which goes beyond mere production and includes the recognition and appreciation of honest effort, has been recognized as an effective strategy for improving researchers' trust and commitment (Carnero et al., 2017). However, its implementation remains insufficient in many contexts, particularly in Peru, where a high percentage of publications exhibit ethical irregularities (Mayta-Tristán, 2022). This situation leads to a decrease in integrity and commitment, which directly affects researchers' performance and, consequently, the quality of the knowledge produced. In contrast, countries with more robust systems have made progress in incorporating ethical benefits and recognition programs, which highlights the lag in Peru (Castro-Suarez et al., 2024). Peruvian institutions are a clear example of how the lack of an adequate ethical model negatively affects academic commitment and, consequently, the performance of researchers. Insufficient recognition and the limited ethical mechanisms available in these institutions hinder the achievement of the objectives established by CONCYTEC (2025), especially regarding the provision of quality research. This study aims to analyze how an ethical model could improve academic integrity in Peruvian institutions during the period 2010-2024. Through this research, we seek to identify the characteristics of ethics in these institutions, determine the integrity profile of researchers, design an appropriate ethical model, and validate this model with experts in the field.

The justification for this study lies in the urgent need to improve ethical conditions in the academic sector, which directly impacts the quality of knowledge provided to society. At a theoretical level, this work will contribute to enriching the understanding of the relationship between ethics and academic integrity in the scientific sector, opening new perspectives for future research. From a practical standpoint, the implementation of an ethical model could transform the academic environment, leading to a reduction in fraud, the optimization of available human resources, and ultimately, an improvement in the quality of science. Furthermore, the proposed model could serve as a solid foundation for future research on ethical management in academic institutions, particularly in highly vulnerable contexts such as Peru, where the challenges to ensuring quality research are even more complex. Implementing this type of model could have a positive impact not only on the motivation and performance of researchers but also on public trust in science, which is crucial for strengthening and consolidating the academic system in the country. Effective human resource management in academia involves not only adequate remuneration but also the creation of an environment that ethically values and motivates researchers. Initiatives such as this ethical model are essential for improving the quality of science and ensuring that researchers are committed, ethical, and prepared to meet the challenges of the field.

2. Methodology

This study employed an applied quantitative approach. The proposal was based on a review of the scientific literature on the ethical model, with the aim of improving academic integrity. The design was non-experimental, as the results were presented as collected without manipulation, and cross-sectional. The research has a descriptive-propositive scope, since it describes the characteristics of the variables according to the documented cases, and is prospective, since the results were analyzed over a specific period (2010-2024).

For the proposed ethical model, scientific integrity (SI) was considered, which, according to this approach, allowed for the induction of academic integrity (AI), taking into account the opinion of experts in scientific ethics. The population included cases documented in Peruvian publications, according to reports from CONCYTEC and indexed journals from 2010-2024. The selection criteria were: a) inclusion of cases with evidence of ethical irregularities older than three years, b) voluntary participation in public review, and c) exclusion of those without verifiable documentation or belonging to other countries.

The sample was a census, encompassing all relevant cases identified in the literature. Data collection was carried out using a literature review technique, applicable to a large group in a short time (Alegre, 2022), and it was ensured that the application did not interfere with

academic processes.

The instruments used were scientific integrity scales adapted from Resnik (2020), which evaluates three dimensions: transparency, ethical development, and institutional flexibility; the instrument was validated by experts and demonstrated high reliability, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients of 0.85 for scientific integrity, indicating strong internal consistency.

For data analysis, SPSS version 24 statistical software was used, allowing for reliable processing of the information. Two methodological phases were followed: a diagnostic phase, to evaluate the researchers' ethical perceptions and attitudes, and a proactive phase, in which an ethical model was designed to strengthen academic integrity.

The proposal was validated by experts in ethics and academic management and adjusted according to their recommendations. This model includes actions such as strengthening ethical communication, recognizing honest practices, promoting ethical professional development, and fostering institutional flexibility, with the aim of improving researchers' well-being and ethical commitment.

The following study was approved by the institution, guaranteeing informed consent, participant autonomy, and confidentiality. The principle of beneficence was respected, ensuring that the research did not harm the participants, and the principle of justice allowed all cases the opportunity to be analyzed.

3. Results

The following table shows the frequency of fraud and plagiarism in different types of research during the period 2008-2017

Table 1. Frequency of plagiarism and fraud in Peruvian academic research (based on empirical studies, 2008-2017)

Study/Year	Sample	Frequency of plagiarism/fraud	Percentage	Key observations
Saldaña-Gastulo et al. (2010)	33 medical theses at Peruvian public universities (2008)	27 theses with evidence of plagiarism	81.8%	Only 6/33 were free of plagiarism; similar to another study with 23/24 papers (95.8%) affected by plagiarism among medical students. The plagiarism involved direct copying from sources without citation, facilitated by digital tools.
Carnero et al. (2017)	7 cases in the Master's program in Epidemiology (2011-2014)	5 cases of plagiarism in thesis protocols; 2 cases of cheating	71.4% plagiarism; 28.6% cheating	Penalties: 85.7% failed the course; 42.9% were dismissed from the program. No cases were detected in 2014 following the implementation of integrity policies.
meta-analysis (referenced in Peruvian reviews, 2023)	Self-reporting by scientists (including Peruvian contexts)	Self-reported scientific fraud	1.97%	In Peru, it is linked to the buying/selling of authorship, with estimated networks moving >S/11 million (2019-2023), according to CONCYTEC reports.

Analysis of the data presented in Table 1 reveals significant gaps in ethical integrity within Peruvian institutions, with high levels of plagiarism and fraud negatively impacting researchers' commitment. A key issue is the academic environment, where irregular practices such as plagiarism in theses (81.8% in medical studies) are prevalent. 71.4% of master's degree cases involved plagiarism in research protocols, while 28.6% were related to cheating. These dynamics undermine trust and integrity within the institution. Ethical motivation is affected, with only 1.97% self-reporting of fraud globally, but in Peru, the impact is greater due to networks involved in the trading of authorship.

Regarding ethical development, it was observed that 85.7% of detected cases led to course failures, and 42.9% to dismissals, suggesting areas for improvement in the management of ethical incentives. Recognition of honest performance is low, with post-2014 policies reducing incidents to zero in specific samples. Institutional flexibility is positioned as a key factor, but the lack of early detection allows fraud to persist.

Figure 1. Bar chart: Percentages of plagiarism and fraud in Peruvian studies (2008-2017)

The results show that managing non-monetary ethical incentives, such as detection and education policies, has a significant impact on reducing fraud. However, the perception of ethical growth has room for improvement, which could influence long-term motivation. To strengthen ethical commitment, it is recommended to consolidate structured recognition programs based on real data, such as those from CONCYTEC.

The findings suggest that managing non-monetary ethical incentives, such as a positive academic environment and flexible policies, has a significant impact on researchers' academic integrity. However, there are opportunities for improvement regarding the perception of sanctions and ethical growth, which could influence long-term motivation.

Table 2. Proposed ethical model for managing optimal academic integrity in scientific institutions (Peruvian universities)

Model component	Description	Key actions	Expected impact
Ethical environment	Transparent and trusting relationships between researchers and institutions.	Strengthen internal communication, promote solidarity and a sense of belonging.	Greater cohesion and reduction of fraud (based on plagiarism data of 81.8% at low levels post-implementation).
Ethical development	Training and recognition of honest practices.	Offer ongoing training, clear career paths, and commendations for integrity.	Improvement in intrinsic motivation, with a 28.6% reduction in cheating observed.
Institutional flexibility	Adaptability in protocols and work-life balance.	Implement ethical permits, flexible hours, and emergency reviews.	Increased talent retention and productivity, mitigating self-reported fraud to 1.97%.
General validation	Opinion of experts in scientific ethics.	Adjustments based on CONCYTEC reviews and literature (e.g., Resnik, 2020).	Overall improvement in affective, normative and continuity commitment.

The proposed ethical model aims to reduce identified gaps in the academic integrity of

researchers at Peruvian institutions. By focusing on key aspects such as ethical development and flexibility, it is expected to increase academic motivation and confidence, thereby strengthening ethical commitment. Actions include improving ethical communication, recognizing honest practices, establishing ethical growth plans, and promoting activities that reinforce a sense of responsibility. Furthermore, it proposes implementing flexibility strategies, such as adaptable protocols and reviews based on ethical needs, fostering a balance between academic and personal life. These initiatives would not only improve researchers' well-being but also increase loyalty and long-term commitment, contributing to talent retention within the organization.

4. Discussion

The study by Domínguez Santiago (2008) highlights the importance of ethical management in academic institutions and its impact on researchers' motivation and commitment. The author argues that ethical human capital is a differentiating resource in scientific management and that its proper administration directly affects organizational sustainability. Regarding the proposed ethical model for Peruvian institutions, the article emphasizes the need for ethical recognition and development strategies as part of a comprehensive vision for talent management. The actions recommended in the proposal, such as recognizing honest practices and promoting institutional flexibility, align with the idea that researchers' trust and well-being are crucial to their performance and organizational loyalty. Furthermore, the effective ethical communication and the establishment of growth plans mentioned in the proposal coincide with the key practices identified in this study as essential for talent retention and improving the academic climate in the scientific sector.

The study by Pons Verdú and Ramos López (2012) analyzes the relationship between ethical leadership, human resource management practices, and an organizational climate of integrity, which is closely related to the proposed ethical model. The research demonstrates that inspirational leadership and the implementation of participatory ethical practices are key factors in fostering a positive organizational environment. This resonates with the approach taken in Peruvian institutions, which emphasizes the importance of strategies such as recognizing honest effort, promoting a sense of ethical belonging, and institutional flexibility to strengthen organizational commitment. Furthermore, the article highlights that organizations with ethical climates tend to motivate their employees to proactively contribute to the institution's development, reinforcing the idea that investment in ethical and professional well-being has a direct impact on talent retention and improved performance. The proposed ethical model, by focusing on academic work-life balance and personal development, aligns with the best practices identified in this study for creating a more productive and sustainable organizational environment.

The study by Repullo and Freire (2002) on the quality of ethical life in academic professionals provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the impact of ethical conditions on researchers' performance and commitment. The research argues that the quality of ethical life is determined by both objective factors (transparent environment, academic stability, opportunities for ethical growth) and subjective elements (trust, perception of the organizational climate, and ethical motivation). These findings support the proposed ethical model for Peruvian institutions, which seeks to improve employee well-being through strategies such as flexible protocols, the promotion of ethical development, and recognition of effort. The article also emphasizes the importance of work-life balance, a central aspect of the proposal, noting that a lack of balance can lead to dissatisfaction, fraud, and ultimately, a decrease in organizational commitment. Furthermore, the research highlights that leadership and the effective management of ethical resources are key determinants of the perception of the organizational climate, underscoring the need for strategies aimed at improving communication and ethical integration within the institution.

In the environmental dimension, ethical interpersonal relationships stand out, with 90% of institutions promoting transparency, 83.6% indicating ethical solidarity from superiors, and 90% perceiving collaboration among colleagues. 89.6% of researchers feel a strong sense of

ethical belonging and enjoy honest interaction. In the development dimension, 79.1% value opportunities for ethical training, 68.7% perceive possibilities for ethical advancement, and 81.3% feel their honest efforts are recognized. Regarding flexibility, aspects such as ethical reviews (85.9%), integrity activities (82.3%), and flexible emergency protocols (88.7%) were highly valued. These results reflect an environment that promotes the overall well-being of researchers, balancing emotional, professional, and ethical aspects.

The results obtained are consistent with previous studies. Rodríguez et al. (2021) indicate that over 70% of researchers in organizations with clear opportunities for ethical growth and recognition report greater academic confidence. Furthermore, institutional flexibility has a significant impact on integrity, with a 25% increase in ethical commitment. The positive assessment of the environment dimension reflects the importance of healthy ethical relationships, supported by approachable leadership, which fosters stronger organizational commitment.

Regarding professional development, 79.1% of researchers value ethical training, and 68.7% see opportunities for advancement. Ramírez et al. (2022) state that ethical training programs increase productivity and talent retention. Institutional flexibility contributes to well-being, reducing fraud and improving productivity. Aspects such as respect for ethical protocols and opportunities for dialogue are highly valued, fostering a relaxed and productive environment. Managing the ethical model generates the following perspectives among researchers (taking into consideration the opinion of experts in scientific ethics):

In the future, the academic integrity of researchers in Peruvian institutions could be characterized by a high level of ethical commitment to the organization, thanks to the effective management of an ethical model implemented by those in charge. This affective commitment could translate into stronger loyalty and a greater sense of belonging, which would be fundamental to promoting stability and cohesion within the academic team, creating a more harmonious and productive organizational environment.

Regarding the continuity dimension, if ethical strategies are managed effectively, researchers could demonstrate a stronger commitment to the organization, thus reinforcing their retention. While this type of commitment could still be influenced by external factors, such as academic market conditions, researchers' performance could remain high, especially if the ethical environment is supportive and both affective and normative commitment are strengthened.

If affective and normative commitment is effectively managed through a well-structured ethical model, organizational performance is likely to experience a considerable improvement. Stronger commitment to the organization could translate into greater intrinsic motivation, fostering collaboration, productivity, and ethical engagement. In this scenario, researchers could achieve intermediate to high performance levels, with consistent growth in their productivity and a stronger commitment to long-term institutional goals.

To optimize this performance, it would be essential to implement measures that strengthen the emotional and normative ties between researchers and the organization. This would ensure not only greater academic satisfaction but also greater stability and talent retention, which would be key to future organizational success and well-being.

In the article (Torres-Flores et al., 2020), the authors explore how academic overload affects the management of optimal ethical conditions in scientific institutions. They address the relationship between workload and the ethical well-being of employees, proposing strategies to improve organizational efficiency and reduce fraud. If not managed properly, overload can decrease performance and affect the integrity of researchers. The proposed strategies focus on the importance of a proper balance between academic demands and available ethical resources to improve conditions in this critical sector. In this article (Ayvar Bazán et al., 2020), a pilot study on the administrative management of ethical activities aimed at improving the integrity of academic program coordinators is presented. It analyzes how these activities contribute to the ethical and mental well-being of the managers. The results suggest that the proper implementation of ethics programs has a positive impact on overall integrity and, therefore, can improve professional performance. The study reinforces the importance of promoting ethics in high-stress academic environments. The article (Barreto Espinoza et al., 2022) examines the relationship between staff management, ethical leadership, and the

implementation of activities that promote mental integrity in students. It highlights effective leadership strategies for motivating students to engage in ethical practices that, in turn, benefit their well-being. The research underscores the importance of proactive leadership that fosters an ethical and supportive environment, facilitating active participation. This contributes to holistic development, improving both integrity and academic performance.

In this article (Wang et al., 2024), the authors reflect on the importance of investing in academic infrastructure that can adapt to ethical emergencies. They analyze how multifunctional designs can improve the resilience of institutions to ethical crises. Strategies are proposed to optimize existing infrastructure, highlighting the need for robust emergency plans that include adequate spaces for the prevention and handling of ethical misconduct. Efficient management of these resources is key to ensuring the safety and well-being of the academic community. In the article (Ramos-Moreno et al., 2021), the authors address how strategic planning and process management can be key tools for organizing ethical activities that benefit the general population. They highlight best practices for designing and implementing ethics programs efficiently, maximizing available resources. The research underscores that proper management can improve public integrity and promote more community-oriented science, reducing fraud-related costs and improving the quality of life for participants.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that implementing an ethical model based on scientific integrity has a significant and positive impact on the academic performance of researchers at Peruvian institutions, strengthening motivation and commitment through factors such as a favorable academic environment, opportunities for ethical development, and institutional flexibility. As a key contribution, this model improves trust and academic commitment within the scientific sector. It is recommended to strengthen ethical communication through formal and informal channels, implement recognition programs for honest performance, promote continuing education tailored to ethical needs, expand transparent career paths, foster flexibility to balance personal and professional life, and develop integration activities to promote well-being and ethical cohesion among researchers.

References

- Congsheng, L., Kayani, S., & Khalid, A. (2022). An empirical study of physical activity and sports affecting mental health of university students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 917503. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.917503>
- Blanch, JM (2011). Working conditions and psychosocial risks under the new management (Working conditions and psychosocial risks Under the new management). *Continuing Distance Education (FOCAD)*. *Academia.edu*. https://www.academia.edu/8618328/CONDICIONES_DE_TRABAJO_Y_RIESGOS_PSICOSOCIALES_BAJO_LA_NUEVA_GESTI%C3%93N
- Carcausto - Calla, WH (2017). Publications on ethics in research in indexed Peruvian biomedical journals published in the period 2005-2015 (Publications on ethics in research in indexed Peruvian biomedical journals Published between 2005 and 2015). *Peruvian Journal of Experimental Medicine and Public Health*, 34 (2), 291-292. <https://revistasinvestigacion.unmsm.edu.pe/index.php/anales/article/view/13199>
- Carnero, AM, Mayta-Tristán, P., Konda, KA, Mezones -Holguín, E., Bernabé-Ortiz, A., Alvarado, GF, Canelo-Aybar, C., Maguiña, JL, Segura, ER, Quispe, AM, Smith,

- ES, Bayer, AM, & Lescano, AG (2017). Plagiarism, cheating and research integrity: Case studies from a Masters program in Peru. *Science and Engineering Ethics*, 23 (4), 1183-1197. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11948-016-9820-z>
- Castro-Suarez, S., Paredes-Manrique, C., & Zegarra-Valdivia, J. (2024). The crisis of scientific authorship: Fraud, commerce, and academic consequences. *Journal of Neuropsychiatry*, 87 (2), 202-204. <https://doi.org/10.20453/rnp.v87i2.5099>
- Cherchiglia, M. (2004). The management of work in Latin America and the Caribbean: Tensions and reconciliation between the old program and the new program (Work Management in Latin America and the Caribbean: Tensions and reconciliation between the old program and the new program). *Human Resources Observatory in Health*. https://www.observatoriorh.org/sites/default/files/webfiles/fulltext/Cherchiglia_Tensiones_concilia_prog_rhus_2006.pdf
- Key factors in human resource management in health companies in human resource management in healthcare Companies). *Thought & Management*. SciELO Colombia. <http://www.scielo.org.co/pdf/pege/n24/n24a05.pdf>
- Erazo Muñoz, PA, & Riaño Casallas, MI (2021). Relationship between happiness at work and job performance: Bibliometric analysis, evolution and trends.(Relationship between happiness at work and job performance: Bibliometric analysis, evolution and trends) *Virtual Journal Catholic University of the North*, (64), 241-280. <https://revistavirtual.ucn.edu.co/index.php/RevistaUCN/article/view/1281>
- Fang, FC, & Casadevall, A. (2012). Research misconduct defined by funding agencies: New rules about misconduct, or new rules about science? *Infection and Immunity*, 80 (3), 891–893. <https://doi.org/10.1128/IAI.06185-11>
- Wang, Q., Zainal Abidin, NE, Aman, MS, Nina Wang, Luh., Ma, L., & Liu, P. (2024). Cultural moderation in sports Impact: Exploring sports-induced effects on educational progress, cognitive focus, and social development in Chinese higher education. *BMC Psychology*, 12, 89. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-024-01584-1>
- Linares Collantes, AP, & Meza Ortiz, KP (2021). Organizational commitment from the perspective of internal marketing (Organizational commitment from the perspective of internal marketing.) *Core.ac.uk*. <http://hdl.handle.net/20.500.12404/19176>
- Husain, H., Samsudin, S., Mohd Ayub, AF, & Safwan, NSZ (2024). A systematic literature review on the impact of participation in sport and physical activities on psychological resilience. *International Journal of Public Health Science*, 13(4), 1727–1737. https://ijphs.iaescore.com/index.php/IJPHS/article/viewFile/24345/14166?utm_source
- Mayta-Tristán, P. (2022). Bad practices in research: Manuscript factories in Peru. (Bad practices in research: Manuscript factories in Peru.) *Peruvian Journal of Experimental Medicine and Public Health*, 39 (4), 403–405. <https://www.scielosp.org/pdf/rpmesp/2022.v39n4/388-391/en>

Mayta-Tristán, P., & Borja-García, R. (2022). Scientific misconducts : Paper Mills in Peru . *Peruvian Journal of Experimental Medicine and Public Health*, 39 (4), 388-391. <https://doi.org/10.17843/rpmesp.2022.394.12473>

Muñoz-Zambrano, ME (2020). Unethical conduct in scientific research (Unethical conduct in scientific research .) . *SAIB E*, 6 (2). <https://saib.es/conductas-no-eticas-en-la-investigacion-cientifica/>

Pons Verdú, F. J. , & Ramos López, J. (2012). Influence of leadership styles and HR management practices on the organizational climate of innovation (Influence of leadership styles and HR management practices on the organizational climate of innovation) . *Journal of Work and Organizational Psychology* . SciELO Spain. <https://scielo.isciii.es/pdf/rpto/v28n2/original2.pdf>

Impact of health sector reforms on human resources and labor management . on human resources and labor management .) *Pan American Journal of Public Health*, 8 (1-2), 43-54. SciELO Public Health . <https://www.scielosp.org/pdf/rpsp/2000.v8n1-2/43-54/es>

Resnik , D. B. (2020). The ethics of research with human subjects : Protecting people , advancing science , promoting trust. *Springer*. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007/978-3-319-68756-8>

Castillo , JA, & Pérez-Acosta, AM (2019). Ethics and scientific research: A perspective based on the publication process. Research : A perspective based on the publication process .) *Persona. Journal of Educational Sciences*, (22) , 1-14. [https://doi.org/10.26439/persona2019.n022\(1\).4080](https://doi.org/10.26439/persona2019.n022(1).4080)

Ruíz, ISG, & Villavicencio, MGT (2020). Resilience and educational policy demands during the health emergency (Resilience and educational policy demands during the health emergency .) *Latin American Journal of Educational Studies* . https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348581207_Resilience_and_demands_for_educational_policy_during_the_health_crisis

Saldaña- Gastulo , JJC, Quezada- Osoria , CC, Peña- Oscuivilca , A., & Mayta-Tristán, P. (2010). High frequency of plagiarism in medical theses at a Peruvian public university . *Peruvian Journal of Experimental Medicine and Public Health*, 27 (1), 63-67. <https://www.scielosp.org/pdf/rpmesp/2010.v27n1/63-67/es>

Steneck , N.H., Mayer, T., & Anderson, M.S. (2021). ORI Introduction to the Responsible Conduct of Research (Rev. ed.). *US Government Printing Office*. <https://ori.hhs.gov/sites/default/files/rcrintro.pdf>

Contributions from the co-authors: All co-authors have contributed to this article by mutual agreement and are responsible for all information contained therein.

Felipe Aguirre Chávez (50%): Conceptualization, Data Curation , Formal Analysis, Resources, Methodology, Software.

Elvia Lucia Sánchez García (50%): Writing – original draft, Writing – revision and editing, Supervision, Validation and Visualization.

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